

Epoxidation and Cleavage of α,β - and β,γ -Unsaturated Sulphones : A Kinetic Study[†]

D. SRI RAMA RAO

Department of Chemistry, Pachaiyappa's College, Madras-600 030

Manuscript received 25 March 1982, revised 5 November 1982, accepted 19 March 1983

Kinetics of epoxidation of a few substituted α,β - and β,γ -unsaturated sulphones by alkaline H_2O_2 in methanol has been studied between 25-40°. The epoxidation follows second order kinetics. The influence of substituents in the phenyl ring on the reaction rate is discussed in terms of reaction mechanism. The oxidative cleavage of a few epoxy sulphones by hydroperoxide anion has also been studied. Adherence to second order kinetics was excellent in every case and the rates were slower than the corresponding epoxidation. β,γ -Unsaturated sulphones undergo immediate cleavage producing C_6H_5CHO and other oxidation products. This is attributed to the weakening of the inductive effect of the sulphonyl function and the complete absence of its mesomeric effect due to the intervening methylene group. The thermodynamic parameters have been calculated for the epoxidation reaction.

ALL the addition reactions to the α,β -unsaturated sulphones that have been documented can be considered to be initiated by nucleophilic attack at the carbon β to the $>SO_2$ group¹. An important factor promoting these reactions must be the stabilization of the resulting carbanion on the α -carbon by the $>SO_2$. These reactions are similar to addition to α,β -unsaturated aldehydes and ketones^{2,3}. Although a few α,β -epoxy sulphones have been prepared from α,β -unsaturated sulphones using alkaline H_2O_2 there is no report in the literature on the study of the kinetics of epoxidation of α,β - and β,γ -unsaturated sulphones and oxidative cleavage of these epoxy sulphones. Hence a systematic kinetic study will serve to elucidate the stereochemical and mechanistic features of epoxidation of unsaturated sulphones and the epoxide ring opening.

Experimental

α,β -Unsaturated sulphones (*trans* isomers) were prepared according to the method of Balasubramanian and Baliah⁴ while the β,γ -unsaturated sulphones were obtained by the method of Rupe and Burgain⁵.

The epoxides were prepared by treating the α,β -unsaturated sulphones with alkaline H_2O_2 (30% aqueous solution) at 30° and cooling to room temperature. The reaction mixture was diluted with water, cooled to 5° and left overnight. The product was filtered and recrystallised from CCl_4 -hexane (1 : 1). 1,2-Epoxy-2-(phenyl sulphonyl)-1-phenyl ethane (epoxystyryl phenyl sulphone). m.p. 103-105° (lit⁴, m.p. 102-104°). 1,2-Epoxy-2-(phenyl sulphonyl)-1-chlorophenyl ethane (epoxy-*p*-chlorostyryl phenyl

sulphone), m.p. 105-106°. (Found : C, 57.0 ; H 3.50 ; S, 10.60. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{11}O_2S$; C, 57.06 ; H, 3.76 ; S, 10.86%). 1,2-Epoxy-2-(phenyl sulphonyl)-1-*m*-nitrophenyl ethane (epoxy-*m*-nitrostyryl phenyl sulphone), m.p. 120-122°. (Found : C, 55.13 ; H, 3.68. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{11}O_2SN$; C, 55.07 ; H, 3.63%). 1,2-Epoxy-2-(*p*-tolyl sulphonyl)-1-phenyl ethane (epoxystyryl *p*-tolyl sulphone), m.p. 156-158° dec. (lit⁴, 155-158° dec). 1,2-Epoxy-2-(*p*-tolyl sulphonyl)-1-*p*-chlorophenyl ethane (epoxy-*p*-chlorostyryl *p*-tolyl sulphone), m.p. 130-132.5°. (Found : C, 58.39 ; H, 4.30. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{13}O_2S$; C, 58.33 ; H, 4.24%). 1,2-Epoxy-2(*p*-tolyl sulphonyl)-1-*m*-nitrophenyl ethane (epoxy-*m*-nitrostyryl *p*-tolyl sulphone), m.p. 118-119°. (Found : C, 56.46 ; H, 4.10 ; S, 10.02. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{13}O_2SN$; C, 56.43 ; H, 4.10 ; S, 10.02%). The ir absorption of these epoxides showed a strong sulphonyl band at 1300 and 1140 cm^{-1} (lit⁴, 1310 and 1140 cm^{-1}) and epoxide bands at 1240, 830 and 790 cm^{-1} (lit⁷, 1240, 830 and 790 cm^{-1}).

UV and tlc techniques have been employed both for the kinetic and analytical studies.

The general procedure is the same as that reported earlier⁴.

Results and Discussion

The second order rate constants k_2 are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

[†] A part of this paper was presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, 1981, Madras.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE EPOXIDATION OF α,β -UNSATURATED SULPHONES

Substrate [†]	$k_2 \times 10^3$ (1/mole. sec)
$C_6H_5CH=CHSO_2C_6H_5$	5.37
$o-ClC_6H_4CH=CHSO_2C_6H_5$	9.26
$p-ClC_6H_4CH=CHSO_2C_6H_5$	8.07
$o-NO_2C_6H_4CH=CHSO_2C_6H_5$	8.84
$m-NO_2C_6H_4CH=CHSO_2C_6H_5$	19.10
$p-NO_2C_6H_4CH=CHSO_2C_6H_5$	27.80
$C_6H_5CH=CHSO_2C_6H_4NO_2-p$	6.25
$C_6H_5CH=CHSO_2C_6H_4CH_3-p$	2.78
$p-ClC_6H_4CH=CHSO_2C_6H_4CH_3-p$	4.58
$m-NO_2C_6H_4CH=CHSO_2C_6H_4CH_3-p$	12.70

[†]trans isomers; [substrate] = 2.0×10^{-3} M; $[H_2O_2]$ = 2.9×10^{-3} M; Temp = 30°; solvent = MeOH.

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE EPOXIDATION OF α,β -UNSATURATED SULPHONES-25-40°

Substrate X	$k_2 \times 10^3$ lit mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹			
	25°	30°	35°	40°
X - $C_6H_4CH=CHSO_2C_6H_5$				
H	3.34	5.57	8.42	12.9
p-Cl	6.27	8.07	11.50	16.7
m-NO ₂	19.20	19.10	24.30	29.0
X - $C_6H_4CH=CHSO_2C_6H_4CH_3-p$				
H	1.86	2.78	4.57	7.59
p-Cl	2.88	4.58	6.31	8.91
m-NO ₂	14.00	12.70	18.20	22.20

[Substrate] = 2.0×10^{-3} M; $[H_2O_2]$ = 2.9×10^{-3} M
Solvent: MeOH.

Effect of structural variation :

α,β -Unsaturated sulphones : *p*-Tolyl sulphones have lower rates than the corresponding phenyl sulphones (Table 1). This is to be expected because the *p*-tolyl group is slightly more electron releasing than the phenyl group and the phenylsulphonyl group exerts a relatively greater inductive effect on the ethylenic bond than *p*-tolyl sulphonyl. This decreases the positive charge on the β -carbon and consequently lowers the rate of epoxidation.

In all the cases, the rate constants for $RSO_2-CH=CHC_6H_4X$ (R=phenyl or *p*-tolyl), $x=o-, m-, p-NO_2$ or $o-, p-Cl$) are more than those for the corresponding unsaturated sulphones, $RSO_2CH=CHC_6H_5$ (R=phenyl or *p*-tolyl). This increase seems to be due only to the inductive effect of the substituents. It is of interest to note that the $-NO_2$ group has a considerable activating effect when it is attached to the *p*-position of the benzene ring directly to the ethylenic carbon atom, than when it is in *p*-position of benzene ring attached to the sulphonyl group.

β,γ -Unsaturated sulphones : Cinnamyl phenyl sulphone, cinnamyl *p*-tolyl sulphone and *p*-chlorophenyl cinnamyl sulphone were studied as substrate for the epoxidation reaction. The rates of epoxidation were so low that they could not be measured under the experimental conditions employed for measuring the

rates for the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated sulphones. On the other hand they were found to undergo immediate cleavage producing C_6H_5CHO and other oxidative products.

In the case of β,γ -unsaturated sulphones the intervening methylene group between sulphonyl group and the ethylenic linkage lowers the stability of the carbanion on the α -carbon, which may result in the fission of ring, producing oxidative products. Similar observations were made during the study of the addition of bromine to several unsaturated sulphones. The increase in the value of $k_{\beta,\gamma}$ over $k_{\alpha,\beta}$ is to be attributed to the weakening of the inductive effect of the sulphonyl group in the β,γ -unsaturated sulphones⁹.

Mechanism of epoxidation :

The epoxidation proceeds by the slow initial attack of HO_2^\ominus anion on the β -carbon atom followed by ring closure and elimination of OH^\ominus anion from the adduct as was observed in α,β -unsaturated ketones^{9,10}. $H_2O_2 + OH_2^\ominus \rightleftharpoons HO_2^\ominus + H_2O$

These epoxidations were shown to be a stereo selective process i.e., irrespective of the configuration of the starting materials a single stereoisomer of the product was obtained⁴.

The log of the rate constants for the reaction correlates reasonably with the Hammett ' ρ ' values of the substituents with a slope ' ρ ' equal to +0.92.

Temperature dependence :

The reactions were studied between 25-40° with a few representative compounds (Table 2). A plot of log k vs $1/T$ indicate that these reactions exhibit an Arrhenius dependence.

The thermodynamic parameters calculated are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Substrate X	E_a k. cal/ mole	ΔH^\ddagger k. cal/ mole	ΔS^\ddagger k. cal/ mole	ΔG^\ddagger k. cal/ mole	Correlation coefficient
X - $C_6H_4CH=CHSO_2C_6H_5$					
H-	16.7	16.1	-16	20.8	0.999
p-Cl-	11.9	11.3	-31	20.4	0.96
m-NO ₂ -	5.0	4.4	-52	19.8	0.98
X - $C_6H_4CH=CHSO_2C_6H_4CH_3-p$					
H-	17.0	16.4	-16	21.2	0.98
p-Cl-	14.0	13.4	-25	20.9	0.97
m-NO ₂ -	5.62	5.03	-50	20.0	0.97

Values calculated using Micro computer 200 of Hindustan Co. Ltd.

The values of ΔG^\ddagger for two sulphone series are more or less of the same order and may be understood in terms of the isokinetic relationship¹¹. The isokinetic temperature, β , values (Table 4) obtained are quite near the experimental range of 298-313 K.

TABLE 4—ISOKINETIC TEMPERATURE

System	β K
Substituted styryl phenyl sulphones	312
Substituted styryl <i>p</i> -tolyl sulphone	320

However, the dependence of ' ρ ', the Hammett reaction constant, on temperature (Table 5) reveals an interesting variation of values which decreases with increasing temperature. Thus, one can at best conclude from the above results that in the working region structural effects become less predominant with the increase in temperature.

 TABLE 5—HAMMETT ' ρ ' VALUES

Temp. °C	Substituted	
	Styryl phenyl sulphone	Styryl <i>p</i> -tolyl sulphone
25	1.00	1.26
30	0.92	0.85
35	0.67	0.75
40	0.50	0.65

TABLE 6—RATE CONSTANTS FOR EPOXIDATIVE-CLEAVAGE

Substrate	$k_2 \times 10^4$ (1/mole sec)
$C_6H_5CH-CHSO_2C_6H_5$	1.11
<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CH-CHSO ₂ C ₆ H ₅	2.22
<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CH-CHSO ₂ C ₆ H ₅	5.56
$C_6H_5CH-CHSO_2C_6H_4CH_3-p$	0.89
<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CH-CHSO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	1.39
<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CH-CHSO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	8.33

[Substrate] = 2.0×10^{-3} M; [H₂O₂] = [NaOH] = 2.9×10^{-3} M;
Temp. 30°; Solvent = MeOH.

Epoxide cleavage :

The oxidative-cleavage of a few substituted α,β -epoxy sulphones by HO₂[⊖] anion have been studied and the results are given in Table 6. The oxidative product identified was benzenesulphonic acid. The epoxide ring opening is determined by the ease with which the C-O bond is ruptured. This is facilitated when there are electron-donating groups. The direction of epoxide ring opening is governed usually by the relative stability of the intermediates.

Mechanism of cleavage :

The oxidative-cleavage of α,β -epoxy sulphones proceeds by the slow initial attack of HO₂[⊖] anion on the α -carbon atom (A) followed by the rupture of C-O bond just as in the cleavage of epoxy ketones¹⁰. A Hammett plot between log *k* and the ' σ ' values of the several substituents shows a good fit and the slope of this line is +0.68, showing an anionic transition state.

On the other hand, in the case of β,γ -epoxy sulphones (unstable) the attack is more likely to be on γ -carbon atom (B) where the electron density is

less. This will also account for one of the products in the reaction being benzaldehyde.

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the author are due to Prof. Sp. Shanmuganathan for facilities, Prof. N. Venkatasubramanian, Vivekananda College, Madras for valuable suggestions and the U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

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